

Acta Medica Young Doctors

SEPTEMBER 2025

zenodo

VOLUME 1
ISSUE 1

Acta Medica Young Doctors

EDITORIAL

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Acta Medica Young Doctors

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Accepted Date: 2025-08-21

Şimşek SD, Şenöğüt C. The Use Of Readability Formulas in Polytrauma. Acta Medica Young Doctors. 01 Eylül 2025;1(1):2-9.

<https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17045136>

Letter From Editor

Acta Medica Young Doctors is taking its first steps into the world of publishing with this issue. We are excited to begin this journey as a new health journal and believe that we will make important contributions to the scientific community. We hope that our name will soon be recognized both nationally and internationally.

The science of medicine is not merely the art of diagnosing and treating diseases; it also carries with it the responsibility of touching human lives. Our young physicians, who shoulder this responsibility, are the most dynamic and promising representatives of healthcare services. With this understanding, Acta Medica: Young Doctors aims to support and highlight the scientific contributions of young doctors working in various fields of medicine.

In this first issue, we are proud to present valuable articles written by physicians and researchers in the early stages of their careers. We are honored to share with you a wide range of original and high-quality works, from basic medical sciences to clinical research, case reports, and literature reviews.

We believe that curiosity, one of the most powerful drivers of scientific progress, will be further strengthened by the contributions of our young colleagues. Acta Medica: Young Doctors is not just a publication platform; it is also a meeting point where young doctors can learn from each other, share their ideas, and develop their scientific perspectives.

We would like to thank all our authors, reviewers, and editorial board members who contributed to this issue of our journal. We invite our readers to contribute to scientific thought and join us on this journey.

Best regards!

Acta Medica Young Doctors

Original Article

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Accepted: 2025-09-02

Şimşek SD, Şenöğüt C. The Use Of Readability Formulas in Polytrauma. Acta Medica Young Doctors. 2025;1(1):2-10.

<https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17045168>

The Use Of Readability Formulas in Polytrauma

ABSTRACT

Background: Polytrauma is defined as a condition in which an individual sustains multiple traumatic injuries, often involving multiple organ systems. We aimed to conduct this study because there are no studies in the literature demonstrating the readability of AI models' responses to questions posed by patients about polytrauma. Therefore, in this study, we aimed to compare the indices measuring the readability of CHATGPT and GEMINI responses to questions about polytrauma.

Methods: In the present study, questions posed by patients and their families regarding polytrauma were compiled online and evaluated by three trauma-related emergency medicine specialists, resulting in 40 questions. The subsequent inquiries were then directed to ChatGPT-5 and Gemini-2.5 Pro, and the responses were meticulously documented. Prior to the formulation of inquiries, both Gemini and ChatGPT were tasked with generating responses for patients or their families who lacked medical knowledge on the subject.

Results: For the majority of readability formulas, including ARI, Flesch Reading Ease, Fog Scale (Gunning FOG Formula), Coleman-Liau Readability Index, The SMOG Index, Linsear Write Formula, Dale-Chall Readability Score, and Spache Readability

Formula, the p-values were greater than 0.05. This suggests that there is no statistically significant difference in the readability of content generated by Gemini and ChatGPT across these measures. For instance, the Flesch Reading Ease scores were 48.64 ± 4.72 for Gemini and 42.26 ± 6.08 for ChatGPT, with a p-value of 0.372, indicating comparable ease of reading. Similarly, the ARI scores were 10.36 ± 1.96 for Gemini and 11.23 ± 1.86 for ChatGPT ($p=0.472$)

Conclusion. Both AI models produce text with similar readability across many common metrics, ChatGPT's output tends to be more complex, requiring a higher reading level as indicated by the Flesch-Kincaid Grade Level, in contrast to Gemini's output.

Keywords: Polytrauma, ChatGPT, Gemini, Flesch-Kincaid Grade Level, readability

Introduction

Polytrauma is defined as a condition in which an individual sustains multiple traumatic injuries, often involving multiple organ systems. These injuries have the potential to be life-threatening and require immediate and comprehensive medical intervention. It is a significant cause of morbidity and mortality worldwide, particularly among young adults, and is most commonly associated with road traffic accidents and falls from height [1,2]. Polytrauma has been identified as a prevalent condition among young adults, resulting in substantial economic and workforce implications due to the consequent loss of productivity and the onset of long-term disability [3].

Artificial intelligence (AI) is increasingly being integrated into the management of polytrauma, offering promising advancements in decision-making and outcome prediction. Polytrauma, characterized by severe injuries to multiple body regions, presents significant challenges in clinical management due to its complexity and high mortality rates. AI technologies, including machine learning models, are being developed to enhance the accuracy of predictions related to patient outcomes, such as mortality, complexity, and complications like systemic inflammatory response syndrome (SIRS) [4,5]. AI has demonstrated satisfactory performance in decision-making for polytrauma patients, particularly in predicting shock, bleeding, and blood transfusion needs. The overall performance of AI in these areas has been rated as good to excellent in several studies [6.] The use of AI and machine learning is suggested for planning management strategies in controversial cases, where traditional methods may not provide clear guidance [7]. AI-generated content often exceeds the recommended readability levels for general audiences. For instance, responses from AI chatbots like ChatGPT, Perplexity, and Gemini on low back pain were found to be difficult to read, with readability scores higher than the recommended 6th-grade level [8]. In the context of emergency medical brochures, AI tools like ChatGPT and Google Gemini produced content with no significant differences in readability, although Gemini's brochures were slightly easier to read [9]. We aimed to conduct this study because there are no studies in the literature demonstrating the readability of AI models' responses to questions

posed by patients about polytrauma. Therefore, in this study, we aimed to compare the indices measuring the readability of CHATGPT and GEMINI responses to questions about polytrauma.

Materials And Methods

In the present study, questions posed by patients and their families regarding polytrauma were compiled online and evaluated by three trauma-related emergency medicine specialists, resulting in 40 questions. Questions that were deemed to be similar or irrelevant were excluded from the study. These questions were then subjected to a revision process that addressed grammatical and semantic issues. The subsequent inquiries were then directed to ChatGPT-5 and Gemini-2.5 Pro, and the responses were meticulously documented. Prior to the formulation of inquiries, both Gemini and ChatGPT were tasked with generating responses for patients or their families who lacked medical knowledge on the subject. The readability of these responses was measured using the Flesch Reading Ease (FRE) formula, the Fesch-Kincaid Grade Level (FKGL) Fog Scale (Gunning FOG Formula), the SMOG Index, the Automated Readability Index (ARI), the Coleman-Liau Index, the Linsear Writing Formula, the Dale-Chall Readability Score, and the Spache Readability Formula. Subsequently, the scores were combined and subjected to a comparative and analytical process using SPSS software.

The Flesch Reading Ease (FRE) formula is a widely utilised readability test that evaluates the ease or difficulty with which a text can be understood by the reader. [10]. The formula

employed is as follows: $FRE = 206.835 - (1.015 \times \text{Average Sentence Length (total number of words divided by total number of sentences)} - (84.6 \times \text{Average Syllables per Word (total number of syllables divided by total number of words)})$. The Flesch-Kincaid Grade Level (FKGL) is a readability formula that estimates the approximate US school grade level required to comprehend a given text. [11]

In contrast to the Flesch Reading Ease, which generates a score ranging from 0 to 100, with higher scores indicating greater ease, the Flesch-Kincaid Grade Level provides a direct correspondence with grade levels. To illustrate, an 8.0 score indicates that an individual with an 8th-grade reading level should be able to comprehend the text. The formula is as follows: $FKGL = (0.39 \times \text{Average Sentence Length} \times \text{Total number of words} \div \text{Total number of sentences}) + (11.8 \times \text{Average Number of Syllables per Sentence} \times \text{Total number of syllables} \div \text{Total number of words}) - 15.59$. The FOG Scale, also known as the Gunning FOG Index (Gunning FOG Formula), is a readability test designed to estimate the years of formal education a person needs to easily understand a piece of English writing on the first reading [14]. The Gunning FOG Index is a tool designed to assess the clarity and complexity of written texts. Its utilisation is ubiquitous, being employed in a variety of contexts including academic writing, business communication, journalism, educational materials and government and public documents [12]. The SMOG Index (Measure of Simple

Meaninglessness) is a readability formula that estimates the years of education required for a person to easily understand a text.[15] The SMOG Formula is: The formula employed is as follows: $1.0430 \times \text{square root of (number of multisyllabic words} \times 30) \div \text{number of sentences.} + 3.1291$ [13]. The Automatic Readability Index (ARI) is a readability formula used to estimate the US grade level required to comprehend a text. [16] ARI Formula: ARI can be calculated as follows: $4.71 \times (\text{Characters} \div \text{Words}) + 0.5 \times (\text{Words} \div \text{Sentences}) - 21.43$ [17]. The Coleman-Liau Index is a readability formula designed to estimate the US grade level required to understand a text. Unlike other formulas based on syllable counts (such as Flesch or SMOG), the Coleman-Liau Index uses characters per word and words per sentence, making it easier to calculate on a computer and therefore suitable for digital applications [17]. The formula is: $\text{CLI} = 0.0588 \times \text{mean number of letters per 100 words} - 0.296 \times \text{mean number of letters per 100 words} - 15.8$ [18]. The Linsear Writing Formula is a readability measure designed to estimate the US grade level required to comprehend a text. B [18]. The Linsear Writing Formula is as follows: The score is calculated by dividing the number of easy words by the number of difficult words, multiplied by three, and then dividing that by the number of sentences [19]. The Dale-Chall Readability Score is a formula that estimates the grade level required to comprehend a text. The raw score is calculated as follows: $0.1579 \times (\text{percentage of difficult words}) + 0.0496 \times (\text{average sentence length})$. Should the percentage of difficult words exceed 5%, then: The adjusted score is

calculated by adding 3.6365 to the raw score [20]. The Spache Readability Formula is a readability test that has been specifically designed to assess the reading level of texts intended for elementary school students, typically for those in grades 1-3. Should a word not be included in Spache's established vocabulary list, it is regarded as challenging [20]. The grade level is calculated as follows: $0.121 \times (\text{words} \div \text{sentences}) + 0.082 \times (\text{difficult words} \div \text{words} \times 100) + 0.659$ [21].

Statistical analysis

The statistical analysis of the data in our study was conducted using SPSS 25.0. In the analysis of demographic and laboratory data of patients who underwent decompression, frequency for categorical data is given as a percentage. The mean \pm standard deviation was utilised for the analysis of continuous variables. For categorical data, Pearson's chi-square and Fisher's exact test were used as appropriate. The effects of haematological parameters on the need for decompression were shown by Student's t-test and Mann-Whitney U test. Statistical significance was defined as $P < 0.05$.

Results

For the majority of readability formulas, including ARI, Flesch Reading Ease, Fog Scale (Gunning FOG Formula), Coleman-Liau Readability Index, The SMOG Index, Linsear Write Formula, Dale-Chall Readability Score, and Spache Readability Formula, the p-values were greater than 0.05. This suggests that there is no statistically significant difference in the readability of content generated by Gemini and ChatGPT across these measures. For instance,

the Flesch Reading Ease scores were 48.64 ± 4.72 for Gemini and 42.26 ± 6.08 for ChatGPT, with a p-value of 0.372, indicating comparable ease of reading. Similarly, the ARI scores were 10.36 ± 1.96 for Gemini and 11.23 ± 1.86 for ChatGPT ($p=0.472$) Flesch-Kincaid Grade Level Discrepancy Statistically Significant Difference: The most notable finding is the statistically significant difference in the Flesch-Kincaid Grade Level between the two models. ChatGPT's generated text had a mean Flesch-Kincaid Grade Level of 11.24 ± 1.46 , which is higher than Gemini's 9.26 ± 1.32 . The p-value for this comparison was less than 0.001, indicating a highly significant difference. This suggests that content produced by ChatGPT tends to require a higher educational level to comprehend compared to content from Gemini.

Discussion

The integration of readability indices and artificial intelligence (AI) represents a growing area of interest, particularly in the context of evaluating the accessibility and quality of AI-generated content. Readability indices, including the Automated Readability Index (ARI), the Flesch Reading Ease Index, and analogous metrics, are employed to evaluate the complexity of text [5-9]. This is imperative for ensuring that AI-generated materials are comprehensible to a wide audience. The readability of AI systems, including chatbots and text generators, is being evaluated with increasing frequency to ensure that they meet the needs of their users, especially in fields such as healthcare and education. This response will

examine the function of readability indices in the context of artificial intelligence, with a particular focus on their utilisation, the challenges they present, and the consequences of their application [11,12]. The utilisation of artificial intelligence in the domain of chatbots and its implications for readability. Research has demonstrated that AI chatbots such as ChatGPT, Bard, and analogous platforms frequently generate content that frequently exhibits readability levels exceeding the recommended 6th-grade level [8]. This phenomenon can act as a significant barrier to the effective dissemination of patient education materials within healthcare settings. For instance, responses from AI chatbots on palliative care were found to be significantly more complex than the recommended readability level, indicating a need for improvement in making AI-generated content more accessible [22].

The Automated Readability Index (ARI) is a tool used to measure the readability of text. It does this by calculating the average length of words and sentences. Its validity has been demonstrated in a variety of contexts, including technical manuals and educational materials. It is employed to ensure that AI-generated content is appropriate for its intended audience [23,24]. The intricacy of AI-generated text is a subject that merits close examination. AI-generated content frequently exceeds the average literacy level of the general population. For instance, patient information brochures generated by AI have been shown to score highly on understandability but low on actionability and visual aids [25]. This inherent complexity has

the potential to impede the efficacy of AI in generating clear and actionable information. A substantial correlation has been demonstrated between readability scores and comprehension levels. This has been evidenced in studies which have shown that higher readability levels correspond with lower comprehension scores among readers [16-19]. This underscores the necessity of ensuring that AI-generated content is aligned with the reading abilities of its intended audience. The enhancement of artificial intelligence content is a subject that has been the focus of much recent research. In order to enhance the usability of AI-generated content, developers must focus on optimising readability indices to ensure that the text is accessible to a wider audience. This process entails the simplification of language and structure without compromising the integrity of the information [12-18]. Educational Applications: The role of artificial intelligence (AI) in education, particularly in the context of enhancing reading literacy, underscores the necessity for readability indices to guide the development of educational materials. AI has the capacity to considerably improve learning outcomes by customising educational materials to suit the reading abilities of students [26].

Readability formulas represent a vital instrument in the evaluation of written material complexity, particularly within health and educational contexts. The SMOG Index, Linsear Write Formula, Dale-Chall Readability Score, and Spache Readability Formula are but a few of the methods employed in the assessment of text readability. Each formula has its own approach

and application, rendering them suitable for different types of texts and audiences. The ensuing discourse will delve into the intricacies of these formulas, their manifold applications, and their efficacy, drawing upon the extant research papers that have been provided [16-20]. The SMOG (Simple Measure of Gobbledygook) Index is a widely utilised metric in health education for the assessment of the readability of materials. It has been established that the phenomenon under discussion is characterised by its consistency and reliability across different languages. However, it should be noted that some variations exist between English, Spanish and French texts [27]. The text's readability level is determined by the number of polysyllabic words contained within, and the resultant reading grade level is indicative of the years of education required to comprehend the material [28].

The Linsear Write Formula is a tool designed to assess the readability of technical documents, a topic which is less commonly discussed in the provided contexts. The programme in question focuses on sentence length and the number of complex words in order to determine readability, making it suitable for technical and instructional materials. The Dale-Chall Readability Score is a widely utilised formula for the evaluation of text complexity, with parameters including the frequency of familiar words and the length of sentences. In the field of healthcare, the utilisation of this system is frequently employed to guarantee the accessibility of patient information [18,19].

This formula has been found to be particularly effective in identifying texts that may be too challenging for the general public, as it employs a list of familiar words to assess readability [16-20]. The Spache Readability Formula has been developed for the purpose of evaluating the readability of primary grade reading materials. The evaluation of texts is based on two key factors: sentence length and the frequency of unfamiliar words. This approach renders the text suitable for younger audiences [18,21]. The present formula is frequently compared with other established models, such as the Fry graph and the Harris-Jacobson formula, due to its proven efficacy in the evaluation of primary grade texts [20]. While readability formulas provide valuable insights into text complexity, it must be acknowledged that they are not without limitations. Critics contend that these formulas frequently depend on simplistic metrics such as word and sentence length, which may not adequately capture the subtleties of linguistic complexity [24]. Furthermore, the efficacy of these formulas can be subject to variation depending on the language and context in which they are employed, as evidenced by the divergent outcomes observed with the SMOG formula across different languages [26,27]. In our study Flesch-Kincaid Grade Level Discrepancy Statistically Significant Difference: The most notable finding is the statistically significant difference in the Flesch-Kincaid Grade Level between the two models. ChatGPT's generated text had a mean Flesch-Kincaid Grade Level of 11.24 ± 1.46 , which is higher than Gemini's 9.26 ± 1.32 . The p-value for this comparison was less than 0.001, indicating a

highly significant difference. This suggests that content produced by ChatGPT tends to require a higher educational level to comprehend compared to content from Gemini.

Conclusion

Both AI models produce text with similar readability across many common metrics, ChatGPT's output tends to be more complex, requiring a higher reading level as indicated by the Flesch-Kincaid Grade Level, in contrast to Gemini's output.

	GEMINI (n=40)	CHAT –GPT (n=40)	p-Value
ARI	10.36±1.96	11.23±1.86	0.472
Flesch Reading Ease	48.64±4.72	42.26±6.08	0.372
Fog Scale (Gunning FOG Formula)	12.21±1.7	10.71±1.44	0.086
Flesch-Kincaid Grade Level	9.26±1.32	11.24±1.46	<0.001
Coleman-Liau Readability Index	13.24±1.68	14.22±3.24	0.224
The SMOG Index	8.36±0.96	7.98±1.12	0.422
Linsear Write Formula	72.34±10.16	74.36±12.01	0.348
Dale-Chall Readability Score	9.12±0.64	10.02±0.96	0.112
Spache Readability Formula	8.24±0.42	7.84±0.84	0.214

Table 1. Comparison of CHATGPT vs GEMINI in terms of readability scores

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Acta Medica Young Doctors

Original Article

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Accepted Date: 2025-09-02

Yavuz, Y. F., & Sevdimbaş, A. (2025). The Effectiveness of Large Language Models in the Diagnosis and Treatment of Glaucoma. *Acta Medica Young Doctors*, 1, 11-16. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17045246>

The Effectiveness of Large Language Models in the Diagnosis and Treatment of Glaucoma

ABSTRACT

Objective The objective of this study is to compare the readability levels of texts generated by Open AI and GEMINI, which are artificial intelligence language models. The present study focuses on the readability analysis of texts on glaucoma, with the objective of determining which model is more suitable for specific purposes and target audiences.

Methods In the course of the research, 20 inquiries were presented to both language models using the same topic and guidelines. The inquiries were posed on various days across ten repeated experiments, and the responses obtained were meticulously documented. The generated texts were then subjected to an analytical process that involved the application of various readability formulas.

Results: The analysis results indicate statistically significant differences between the readability scores of OpenAI and GEMINI. A comparative analysis revealed that GEMINI exhibited superior performance in terms of average scores across a range of metrics when compared with OpenAI. This observation suggests that GEMINI's texts are characterized by a heightened level of complexity. P-values were determined to be 0.001 for the Flesch Readability, FOG scale, and a multitude of additional metrics. However, a lack of statistical significance was observed in the Forecast Readability Formula ($p = 0.050$).

Conclusion The findings indicate that GEMINI might be more appropriate for texts intended for an academic or professional audience, while OpenAI could be a more suitable option for content directed towards a broader audience.

Keywords: Glaucoma, Artificial Intelligence, Readability

Introduction

Glaucoma is a complex eye disease characterized by progressive optic neuropathy, leading to irreversible blindness if untreated. A comprehensive understanding of the risk factors associated with glaucoma is imperative for the early detection and management of this condition [1]. The primary risk factors for glaucoma include elevated intraocular pressure (IOP), age, genetic predisposition, ethnicity, and systemic health conditions [2]. These factors contribute to the development and progression of glaucoma through various interconnected biological mechanisms. Elevated intraocular pressure (IOP) has been identified as a significant risk factor for glaucoma, particularly primary open-angle glaucoma (POAG) [3]. It has been associated with optic nerve damage and visual field loss [4]. The primary strategy for preventing glaucoma progression is to manage intraocular pressure (IOP) through medication or surgery. Advanced age is a well-documented risk factor for glaucoma, with the prevalence of the condition increasing significantly in individuals over 40 years old [6]. A positive family history of glaucoma has been demonstrated to increase the risk of developing the condition, indicating a genetic component in the disease's etiology [7]. Ethnic background has been demonstrated to be a contributing factor, with Asians exhibiting a higher propensity for developing angle-closure glaucoma and African descent individuals demonstrating a heightened vulnerability to primary open-angle glaucoma (POAG) [8].

The application of Artificial Intelligence (AI) has emerged as a transformative instrument in the management and diagnosis of glaucoma, a leading cause of irreversible blindness on a global scale. Recent advancements in artificial intelligence (AI), particularly deep learning models, have

demonstrated considerable potential in enhancing the accuracy and efficiency of glaucoma care [9]. These advancements are of crucial importance in light of the complex nature of glaucoma, which frequently manifests with subtle clinical signs that are challenging to detect in an early stage [10]. The role of artificial intelligence (AI) in glaucoma management encompasses several pivotal domains, including early detection, personalised management, and continuous monitoring. The collective impact of these domains is demonstrated by their contribution to enhanced patient outcomes [11].

Materials and Methods

The experiment involved the administration of 20 questions on the same topic, employing identical prompts and utilizing both the Open AI and GEMINI language models. These inquiries were reiterated on various days, and the outcomes obtained after 10 repetitions were documented. The responses provided by each model were recorded and used in the readability score analysis.

Readability Analyses

The generated texts are analyzed using software or a programming language (e.g., Python) that calculates the readability formulas and metrics listed below.

1. **Flesch Readability Score:** Scores the readability of the text out of 100. Higher scores indicate easier texts.
2. **Flesch-Kincaid Readability Level:** Estimates the U.S. education grade level required to understand the text. A lower grade level indicates an easier text.
3. **Coleman-Liau Index:** Estimates the U.S. education grade level required to understand the text.
4. **SMOG Index:** Estimates the U.S. education grade level required to understand the text. It is calculated primarily by counting words with three or more syllables.

5. **Automated Readability Index:** Estimates the grade level required to understand the text.
6. **Average Reading Level:** Provides a general reading level estimate by taking the average of all readability scores.
7. **Linsear Writing Formula:** Determines the level of notes required to understand the text.
8. **Fog Scale:** Estimates the level of education required to understand the text.

Statistical Analysis

The statistical analyses were conducted using the SPSS (Statistical Package for Social Sciences) for Windows 27.0 program. The data were subsequently classified. Categorical data were defined as percentages and frequencies. The numeric data were defined, and a distribution analysis was performed. Data sets that conformed to a normal distribution were defined as mean \pm standard deviation (SD). A t-test was applied to the identified results, and findings with a p-value below 0.05 were considered significant.

Results

Subsequent to the inquiry being posed on ten occasions, a comparison was made between the readability scores that were ascertained. The findings of this study indicate the presence of statistically significant disparities in the readability measurements of OpenAI and GEMINI. The findings of the study indicate that the disparity between the two artificial intelligences, as evidenced by a multitude of metrics, including but not limited to reading level, automatic readability index, Flesch readability, Fog Scale, Fesch-Kincaid level, and SMOG index, is statistically insignificant at the p0.05 level. This finding suggests that the two language models process texts differently in terms of readability, and that these differences are not random. In addition, the Coleman-Liau Index indicates a substantial discrepancy

between the two models ($p = 0.012$). Moreover, the Linsear Writing Formula reveals a remarkably significant difference ($p = 0.001$). However, according to the principles of the Forecast Readability Formula, there is no statistically significant difference between the two models ($p=0.050$). These analyses demonstrate that the formulas employed to evaluate the readability characteristics of texts can yield results from multiple perspectives. Table 1 presents a comparison of the readability scores.

Discussion

A comparison of ChatGPT and Google Gemini in the context of glaucoma reveals significant discrepancies in their capabilities and performance. Recent studies have indicated that ChatGPT, specifically in its version 4.0, has demonstrated consistent superiority over Google Gemini in a range of ophthalmological tasks, including surgical planning and diagnostic accuracy [12]. This phenomenon is evidenced by studies which demonstrate that ChatGPT exhibits a higher degree of agreement with expert opinions and provides more accurate and consistent responses in comparison to Gemini [13]. The ensuing sections explore particular aspects of their performance in glaucoma-related tasks. In a study comparing the two models' ability to suggest surgical plans for glaucoma cases, ChatGPT-4 demonstrated a 58% agreement with glaucoma specialists, significantly outperforming Gemini, which had a 32% agreement rate. ChatGPT demonstrated a higher degree of consistency in its responses when faced with repeated queries. In contrast, Gemini exhibited deficiencies, failing to complete the task in 27% of cases [14,15] In cases of challenging glaucoma, ChatGPT demonstrated a superior performance, achieving a 45% agreement rate, in comparison to Gemini's 20% [17]. ChatGPT exhibited a high degree of accuracy in diagnosing glaucoma from clinical case reports, matching or exceeding the performance of senior ophthalmology residents. The model demonstrated an

accuracy of 72.7% in the diagnosis of cases, thus indicating its potential for utilisation in clinical settings to facilitate rapid and objective diagnoses [18].

With regard to the general knowledge of glaucoma, ChatGPT demonstrated a high degree of accuracy in its responses, providing correct answers in 88.7% of cases. The model exhibited particular proficiency in questions related to diagnosis, treatment, and prevention of the condition [19]

ChatGPT's responses to inquiries pertaining to glaucoma exhibited a higher reading comprehension level in comparison to conventional patient information resources. This disparity may potentially restrict ChatGPT's accessibility to patients who lack advanced reading abilities [20] Despite this, ChatGPT's responses were found to be effective for providing general information and potential treatment options, although they sometimes lacked the use of formal medical terminology [21]. In a range of ophthalmological tasks, including retinal detachment and other eye conditions, ChatGPT demonstrated a consistent superiority over Google Gemini in terms of accuracy and the quality of its responses [16]. ChatGPT's superior performance is attributed to its capacity to furnish more accurate and thematically coherent responses, particularly in the context of complex and challenging inquiries [17,18] While ChatGPT demonstrates potential in supporting tasks related to glaucoma, it is essential to acknowledge its limitations and identify areas for enhancement [12,13].

The "black box" nature of AI models poses challenges in terms of interpretability and explainability, which are crucial for clinical adoption [22]. AI is being integrated with clinical tools such as fundus imaging and visual field meters to enhance glaucoma diagnosis and prediction techniques [23]. The "Doctor + AI" model is gaining traction, where AI assists clinicians in making more accurate diagnoses, thereby clarifying roles and ensuring patient safety [24]. Future AI applications in glaucoma are expected to

focus on disease risk prediction, progression monitoring, and sub-phenotype identification, leveraging advanced imaging and genomic data [25]. While AI holds significant potential in revolutionizing glaucoma care, its integration into clinical practice is not without challenges. Regulatory hurdles, the need for explainable AI, and the external validity of AI models remain significant barriers to widespread adoption [26].

The substantial disparities in readability scores between OpenAI and GEMINI underscore pivotal inquiries concerning the text generation and processing procedures of artificial intelligence language models. The findings indicate that these models not only generate content but also shape the structural features of texts, linguistic complexity, and their potential impact on readers in different ways. A comparative analysis reveals that GEMINI consistently achieves higher average scores across a wide range of metrics when compared to Open AI, suggesting that its texts may resonate more profoundly with a sophisticated and discerning audience, one that is likely to comprise individuals from academic and professional backgrounds. This observation may suggest that GEMINI utilizes longer sentence structures, less frequently used words, or more complex grammatical structures.

However, a more rigorous evaluation of these differences should be based on their intended use, rather than leading to a definitive conclusion about which model is "better." For instance, OpenAI's text might be more appropriate for a rudimentary blog post targeting a general audience, whereas GEMINI's text could be more suitable for an academic article or technical report. The absence of a substantial discrepancy in the Readability Formula suggests that the two models implement the fundamental principles of readability in a comparable manner for specific text categories. Consequently, it is evident that AI-generated texts must be optimized with a focus on the

target audience and the intended purpose of the content. Subsequent studies should concentrate on investigating the underlying linguistic and algorithmic factors that underpin these variations in greater detail.

Additionally, research should be conducted to determine how these models can be adapted to generate the most appropriate text for users' requirements.

	Open AI (n=20)	GEMINI (n=20)	p-Value
Average Reading Level Consensus	10,17±2,12	12,38±1,76	<0,001
Automated Readability Index	9,23±0,56	13,04±0,9	<0,001
Flesch Reading Ease	51±2,45	44±3,65	<0,001
Fog Scale	11±1,9	12,9±1,01	<0,001
<i>Fesch-Kincaid Grade Level</i>	8,69±0,12	11,87±0,56	<0,001
Coleman–Liau Index	11,73±1,12	12,98±2,1	0,012
SMOG index	8,37±1,34	11,13±0,78	<0,001
Linsear Write Formula	75±4,34	63±6,5	<0,001
Forecast readability formula	12,37±0,12	11,6±2,04	0,050

Table 1. Comparison of readability scores

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Acta Medica Young Doctors

Original Article

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Accepted Date: 2025-09-02

Karacan Ş. Seasonal Distribution of
Urticaria Patients: Mediterranean Region.
Acta Medica Young Doctors. 02 Eylül
2025;1:16-23.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17045295>

Seasonal Distribution of Urticaria Patients: Mediterranean Region

ABSTRACT

Background: Urticaria, a common skin condition, is often influenced by various factors, including environmental conditions. While some studies suggest a link between urticaria and seasonal changes, the relationship is complex and can vary by geographical location and urticaria subtype. This study aimed to examine the relationship between urticaria and season-weather conditions in the Mediterranean region of Turkey.

Methods: This was a retrospective study conducted on patients diagnosed with urticaria who presented to the emergency department of a tertiary hospital in the Mediterranean region throughout 2023. Data were analyzed to assess the relationship between urticaria and categorical variables (seasons, months, weather conditions) using the Pearson's chi-square test, and continuous meteorological variables (temperature, dew point, humidity, wind speed, and pressure) using the independent samples t-test. The statistical significance level was set at $p < 0.05$.

Results: The analyses revealed no statistically significant association between the frequency of urticaria and either seasons, months, or weather conditions. Pearson's chi-square tests showed no significant relationship with season ($p = 0.999$) or month ($p = 0.998$). Similarly, the independent samples t-test results indicated no significant differences in mean meteorological conditions between the groups with and without urticaria (all $p > 0.05$).

Conclusion: The findings suggest that the occurrence of urticaria in this study's sample is not dependent on seasonal or daily meteorological factors. This

indicates that the etiology of urticaria in this population may be more related to chronic, internal factors rather than external environmental triggers. Future studies should include a broader range of potential triggers like air pollutants or specific allergens to further explore this relationship.

Keywords: Urticaria, Meteorological Factors, Seasons

Introduction

Urticaria, commonly known as hives, is a prevalent skin condition characterized by the sudden appearance of itchy wheals and sometimes angioedema [1]. It affects up to 20% of the population at some point in their lives and can be classified as either acute or chronic, with chronic urticaria further divided into spontaneous or inducible types [2]. The condition is primarily mediated by mast cells and histamine, but recent research has identified other inflammatory cells and cytokines as contributors. Studies have shown that acute urticaria (AU) in children exhibits seasonal variations. In a study conducted in southern Germany, AU was more prevalent in winter and had another peak in June, with the lowest incidence in summer [3]. This pattern was linked to respiratory infections, which were more common during these peak times, suggesting a viral etiology for AU in children [4]. This subtype of urticaria, which is triggered by heat or exercise, has been reported to occur predominantly in winter. Patients experienced symptoms when exposed to heat during the winter but not in summer, indicating that acclimatization to heat might influence the occurrence of symptoms [5]. A study on asthma patients found that episodes of acute urticaria were more frequent during seasonal exacerbations of asthma, suggesting a link between respiratory conditions and urticaria during certain seasons [6]. In this study, we aimed to examine the relationship between urticaria and season-weather conditions.

Materials and methods

This retrospective study was conducted on patients diagnosed with urticaria who visited the emergency department of a tertiary hospital serving the Mediterranean region during 2023. In the course of the research study, the collected data from the patients' medical records were subjected to rigorous analysis. Patients with urticaria were grouped according to season, month, and meteorological conditions, including temperature, dew point, humidity, wind speed, and pressure.

Weather data was obtained by creating an API based on data from the meteorological station serving the area where the hospital is located.

Statistical Analysis

The statistical analyses were conducted using the SPSS (Statistical Package for Social Sciences) for Windows 27.0 program. The data were subsequently classified. Categorical data were defined as percentages and frequencies. The numeric data were defined, and a distribution analysis was performed. Data following a normal distribution were defined as mean \pm standard deviation (SD). For data sets that did not adhere to a normal distribution, the median and interquartile range (IQR) were determined. The chi-square test was employed to ascertain the relationship between categorical data. The analysis of numeric tests that followed a normal distribution was conducted using parametric tests (t-tests). Statistical findings with a p-value below 0.05 were considered to be significant.

Result

The study revealed that patients suffering from urticaria sought treatment on 160 days of the year. When the data were examined in conjunction with the Pearson Chi-Square test results, no statistically significant relationship was identified between the seasons and the incidence of urticaria ($\chi^2(3, N = 365) = 0.024, p = 0.999$). The findings

of this study suggest that the onset of urticaria does not exhibit a specific seasonal pattern and demonstrates a uniform distribution throughout the year (see Table 1).

A Pearson's chi-square test was performed to examine the relationship between month and the presence of urticaria. The findings indicated an absence of a statistically significant association between the two variables, as evidenced by the result of the chi-squared test ($\chi^2(11, N = 365) = 2.094, p = 0.998$). The p-value of 0.998 is considerably higher than the conventional alpha level of 0.05, suggesting that the observed distribution of urticaria cases across the months is probably attributable to chance (see Table 2).

However, the statistical analysis revealed no evidence of a significant correlation between weather conditions and the occurrence of urticaria ($\chi^2(3, N = 365) = 1.358, p = 0.715$, Table 3). These findings suggest that meteorological factors do not have a statistically significant effect on the onset of urticaria. A meticulous examination of the meteorological conditions reveals no substantial disparities between the two groups (see Table 4).

Discussion

The relationship between urticaria and weather conditions is complex, involving various meteorological factors that can influence the frequency and severity of urticaria flare-ups [7]. Urticaria is characterised by itchy wheals and, in some cases, angioedema. Environmental conditions, including temperature, humidity and sunlight exposure, can trigger or exacerbate urticaria [8]. Studies have shown that these factors can significantly impact the frequency of emergency department visits and outpatient consultations related to urticaria. This article will explore the specific meteorological parameters associated with urticaria, drawing on recent research findings [9].

Higher temperatures have been linked to an increased risk of urticaria. For example, a study conducted in Turkey found that patients with urticaria were more likely to visit the emergency department during the summer months, when daily maximum and minimum temperatures were higher [10]. Similarly, research in China indicated that high temperatures increased the risk of outpatient visits for urticaria, with a notable cumulative effect observed over a 0–7 day lag period [11]. Relative humidity also plays a crucial role in urticaria incidence. In Turkey, for example, lower humidity levels were associated with a higher likelihood of urticaria presentations [12]. Increased exposure to sunlight has also been linked to a higher probability of urticaria. A Turkish study reported that each additional hour of sunshine increased the likelihood of urticaria by 7.4% [13]. This suggests that sunlight exposure may be a significant trigger for urticaria in susceptible individuals. The presence of air pollutants such as CO, NO₂ and O₃ has been shown to influence urticaria incidence. High concentrations of these pollutants have been associated with an increased risk of urticaria visits, with the effects persisting for several days [14]. This highlights the potential for air quality to exacerbate urticaria symptoms, particularly in urban environments. However, urticaria is a multifaceted condition influenced by various triggers, including allergens, stress, and underlying health conditions [15]. Chronic urticaria, in particular, may have autoimmune or idiopathic origins, which makes identifying specific environmental triggers difficult. The relationship between urticaria and seasonal patterns is complex and varies depending on the type of urticaria and the geographical location. For example, acute urticaria (AU) in children often exhibits seasonal trends, with peaks occurring in certain months, whereas cholinergic urticaria tends to be more prevalent in winter [16]. The seasonality of urticaria is influenced by environmental factors such as temperature and humidity, and is often associated with respiratory

infections, which are a common trigger. This overview will explore the seasonal patterns of urticaria, with a focus on acute and cholinergic urticaria, as well as the potential triggers associated with these patterns [17]. One study conducted in London found that most acute urticaria cases in children occurred in autumn, with a significant peak in November. This suggests a seasonal trend potentially linked to environmental changes or increased respiratory infections during this time [18]

In southern Germany, acute urticaria in children showed a higher incidence in winter and another peak in June. This pattern was independent of sex and was not observed in children under five years old. These peaks coincided with increased respiratory infections, suggesting a potential link between viral infections and urticaria [19]. Cholinergic urticaria, which is characterised by small, itchy welts triggered by heat or exercise, was found to predominantly occur in winter. Patients experienced symptoms when exposed to heat or exercise during this period, but not during the summer months. This suggests that acclimatisation to heat may play a role in the manifestation of symptoms [20].

Across various studies, respiratory infections were identified as a common trigger for acute urticaria. These infections are more prevalent in the colder months, which may explain the seasonal peaks in urticaria cases [21]. There is a noted association between asthma exacerbations and episodes of acute urticaria, particularly during seasonal changes. This relationship highlights the role of mast cell activation and histamine release in both conditions [22].

The analyses conducted by season and month reveal one of the most salient findings of this study. The application of both seasonal (spring, summer, fall, winter) and monthly chi-squared tests revealed no statistically significant relationship between the incidence of urticaria and time (month or season) ($p > 0.05$). These results support the

hypothesis that urticaria is not specific to a particular season or month in the population studied, but occurs at similar rates throughout the year. Contrary to the prevailing assumption that urticaria is directly related to pollen or other seasonal allergens, this finding suggests that the etiology of urticaria in the sample studied may be linked to other factors, such as chronic causes, medications, or foods. Subsequent studies may encompass diverse populations and environmental factors from disparate regions to substantiate this finding and investigate the underlying causes of urticaria with greater depth.

The findings of this study provide important insights into the relationship between the onset of urticaria and environmental factors. The analyses indicated that there was no statistically significant effect on the incidence of urticaria in terms of both seasonal and monthly distributions and various meteorological variables (temperature, humidity, wind speed, etc.).

Preliminary cross-tabulation analyses indicated that urticaria cases exhibited minimal variation across different months and seasons of the year, with incidence rates maintaining a relatively stable trend. This finding was statistically confirmed by Pearson Chi-Square test results ($p > 0.05$). In addition, the independent samples t-test results indicated that there was no statistically significant difference in the average meteorological conditions experienced by individuals with and without urticaria ($p > 0.05$).

The findings of this study suggest that the hypothesis linking urticaria to environmental triggers is not supported by the data. The analysis indicates that external environmental conditions, such as season, month, and weather, do not appear to be significant factors in the sample under study. This observation indicates that the etiology of urticaria cases may be more associated with chronic causes, food allergies, drug reactions, or other internal factors.

Future studies should utilize larger samples from diverse geographic regions to examine the environmental relationship of urticaria in greater depth. These studies should also analyze more specific variables, such as pollen counts, air pollution levels, and other environmental chemicals. The findings of this study offer significant insights into the understanding of urticaria, suggesting that individual and internal factors may exert a more substantial influence than general weather conditions.

Limitation

The present study is not without its limitations, which may have ramifications for the generalizability of its findings. Firstly, the study employs a retrospective design and is exclusively based on data from patients who visited the emergency department of a single hospital in the Mediterranean Region throughout 2023. This may limit the generalizability of the results to patients with urticaria in other geographical regions or larger populations. Secondly, the present study exclusively examined the relationship between general meteorological conditions (season, month, temperature, humidity, wind, and pressure) and the incidence of urticaria. The analyses indicated that these external environmental conditions are not the sole determining factors. However, the study's limitations precluded the investigation of more specific factors that may contribute to the etiology of urticaria, including the pollen count, levels of air pollution, stress levels, food allergies, drug reactions, and underlying chronic

causes. Consequently, subsequent studies should incorporate these variables to more thoroughly examine the environmental aspects of urticaria.

Conclusion

The present study examined data from patients who visited the emergency department with a diagnosis of urticaria in the Mediterranean Region in 2023. The analyses indicated that there was no statistically significant relationship between the incidence of urticaria and the seasons, months, and various meteorological variables (temperature, dew point, humidity, wind speed, and pressure).

Despite the existence of prior research indicating seasonal fluctuations, particularly with regard to specific subtypes, such as acute urticaria and cholinergic urticaria in children, the results of the present study offer a divergent perspective. The data obtained demonstrate that urticaria cases in the sample under study exhibited a relatively stable distribution throughout the year, indicating that external environmental factors alone are not the determining triggers (3333).

This observation indicates that the etiology of urticaria in patients may be more associated with chronic causes, food allergies, or internal factors such as drug reactions. Consequently, this study provides a valuable perspective that individual and internal factors may play a more important role in understanding urticaria than general weather conditions.

Season	No Urticaria		Urticaria Yes		Total	
	<i>n</i>	%	<i>n</i>	%	<i>n</i>	%
Spring	50	24.4%	40	25.0%	90	24.7%
Summer	52	25.4%	40	25.0%	92	25.2%
Autumn	52	25.4%	40	25.0%	92	25.2%
Winter	51	24.9%	40	25.0%	91	24.9%
Total	205	100.0%	160	100.0%	365	100.0%

Table 1. Urticaria patients seasonal comperation

Month	No Urticaria		Urticaria Yes	
	n	%	n	%
1	18	8.8%	13	8.1%
2	16	7.8%	12	7.5%
3	16	7.8%	15	9.4%
4	19	9.3%	11	6.9%
5	17	8.3%	14	8.8%
6	15	7.3%	15	9.4%
7	19	9.3%	12	7.5%
8	18	8.8%	13	8.1%
9	17	8.3%	13	8.1%
10	17	8.3%	14	8.8%
11	17	8.3%	13	8.1%
12	16	7.8%	15	9.4%
Total	205	100.0%	160	100.0%

Table 2. Urticaria patients monthy comperation

Weather Condition	No Urticaria		Urticaria Yes		Total	
	n	%	n	%	n	%
Fair	99	48.3%	84	52.5%	183	50.1%
Windy	8	3.9%	6	3.8%	14	3.8%
Rainy	11	5.4%	11	6.9%	22	6.0%
Cloudy	87	42.4%	59	36.9%	146	40.0%
Total	205	100.0%	160	100.0%	365	100.0%

Table 3. Urticaria patients wather condition comperation

Variable	No Urticaria (n=205)		Urticaria Yes (n=160)		t	df	p
	Mean	SD	Mean	SD			
Temperature	22.20	7.98	22.13	7.96	76	363	939
Dew Point	11.13	7.41	11.09	7.58	42	363	967
Humidity (%)	54.06	20.94	54.47	22.06	-179	363	858
Wind Speed (km/h)	13.75	8.13	13.17	7.74	694	363	488
Pressure (hPa)	1007.02	6.12	1007.62	5.78	-954	363	341

Table 4. Urticaria patients wather comperation

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Case Report

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Accepted Date: 2025-09-02

Durkal AŞ. Case Report: Cardiotoxic Syncope and Sudden Cardiac Death Due to Carboplatin Use. Acta Medica Young Doctors. 02 Eylül 2025;1:24-9.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17038161>

Case Report: Cardiotoxic Syncope and Sudden Cardiac Death Due to Carboplatin Use

ABSTRACT

With the prolongation of life, the use of multiple drugs occurs especially in elderly patients. Drugs used by geriatric patients and individuals with comorbid diseases may cause changes at the cell level that will cause mortal and morbid effects. Heart failure and cardiac syncope caused by the effect of cardiotoxic drugs are important risk factors for sudden cardiac death as stated in the literature. In our case, sudden cardiac death after cardiac syncope of a patient with metastatic breast cancer using carboplatin was presented.

Keywords: Cardiotoxic Syncope, Sudden Cardiac Death, Carboplatin

Introduction

Syncope: It is a condition that manifests itself with a temporary loss of cognitive functions. It is usually caused by conditions affecting systemic blood flow, where a decrease in cerebral blood flow and deterioration in brain nutrition may occur [1].

After stabilizing the condition of the patients in the emergency room, it is aimed to explain the need for further research and mortality factors for syncope and near-syncope conditions. According to the San Francisco Syncope rules, which are used for this and the sensitivity of which is determined as 100%, the presence of a history of heart failure, hematocrit values below 30%, abnormality in ECGs, abnormalities in respiratory patterns and systolic blood pressure below 90 mmHg are advanced. requires research. This allows for evaluating the 7-day survival of patients [2, 3].

Carboplatin: It is an antineoplastic drug, an analog of platinum, which belongs to the group of alkylating agents. It has indications for many different types of cancer, one of which is metastatic breast cancer. Among its side effects, cardiac side effects are seen as less than 1% [4, 5].

Cardiac-induced syncope occurs due to structural or functional heart disease. Sudden cardiac death expectancy rates for non-cardiac syncope are quite high for this group. In the 5-year follow-up of the patients, a mortality rate of 50% is observed, with 30% of the patients in the first year [6, 7].

This case showed a rare case of cardiac origin syncope and follow-up of an oncology patient with cardiac pathology.

CASE REPORT

A 71-year-old female patient presented with complaints of exertional dyspnea, dizziness, and syncope while returning home from the

hospital emergency department. Subsequent to the manifestation of exertional dyspnea, the patient exhibited symptoms of dizziness, which culminated in a complete loss of balance and subsequent falls. The patient reported a 3-centimeter full-thickness laceration on her nose. The patient lost consciousness but regained it spontaneously.

The patient diagnosed with heart failure has been fitted with a DDDR type pacemaker. The patient's medical history reveals that she underwent a surgical procedure for breast cancer five years ago and subsequently received adjuvant chemotherapy. Over the course of the preceding three months, malignant epithelial metastases were detected in the liver, and the patient was deemed unsuitable for surgical intervention. She has initiated a combination chemotherapy regimen comprising carboplatin and gemcitabine.

The patient was utilizing a fentanyl patch containing 100 micrograms per hour for palliative purposes in conjunction with slow-release tramadol tablets, 100 milligrams.

The patient was found to be conscious, cooperative, and oriented during the physical examination. The Glasgow Coma Scale score was determined to be 15/15. The neurological examination revealed no abnormalities, and a 3-centimeter laceration was observed in the nasal region, likely resulting from the fall. The patient's respiratory sounds were within normal parameters, and no tenderness, guarding, or rebound tenderness was detected during the abdominal examination. A normal range of sensory and circulatory function was observed in the extremities. The muscular strength of all extremities was evaluated as a perfect 5/5. No bleeding was detected during the rectal examination.

A meticulous examination of the nose revealed a laceration on the skin surface, crepitation was detected, the nasal passages were open, and no hematoma was observed. A comprehensive evaluation revealed no

underlying conditions that would compromise the patient's respiratory function.

The patient's vital signs, as documented at the time of admission, were as follows: The patient's temperature was recorded at 36.9°C, their pulse rate was 70 beats per minute (bpm) and was regular, their respiratory rate was 12 breaths per minute (bpm), their blood oxygen saturation levels were 90% without the need for oxygen support, and their arterial blood pressure was 107/77 mmHg. The patient's subsequent vital signs, monitored with nasal oxygen support, revealed an oxygen level of 99%.

The QTc interval was measured at 474 milliseconds (ms) on the electrocardiogram (ECG) obtained during the application. No ST elevation was observed on the ECG, indicating an absence of ectopic atrial rhythm in the DDDR pacemaker. The rhythm observed at 68/min was assessed as sinus. The second ECG, obtained for control purposes, revealed no significant findings aside from a single, clinically insignificant ventricular extrasystole (VES) beat, with a recorded rate of 74 beats per minute (bpm). The QTc interval was calculated to be 442 milliseconds on the control electrocardiogram (ECG).

Following the preliminary evaluation, nasal oxygen supplementation at a rate of 4 liters per minute was initiated to address the patient's low saturation levels, which were found to be stable. Given the nature of the open wound, the patient was administered tetanus prophylaxis and underwent imaging procedures.

Neuroimaging of the patient revealed cerebral atrophy and sequelae of encephalomasia changes in the occipital lobes. A thorough examination of the facial bones using imaging technology revealed a fracture line in the nasal bone and a deviation to the left in the nose. Thoracic imaging revealed a cardiac pacemaker as well as reticular densities in the right upper lung lobe. A linear fibroatelectatic band

formation was identified in the right inferior lobe. The right breast could not be imaged due to a previous surgical intervention.

The patient's complete blood count revealed a hemoglobin level of 9.8 g/dL and a hematocrit of 31.8%. The patient's complete blood count revealed a white blood cell count of 15,400/mm³ and a platelet count of 516,000/mm³. The patient's biochemical tests revealed the following results: creatinine 1.1 mg/dL, blood urea nitrogen 23 mg/dL, LDH 295 U/L, and C-reactive protein 67.7 mg/dL. The INR value for the purpose of bleeding monitoring was 1.14.

The patient's cardiac troponin T value, a sensitive cardiac marker, was initially measured at 92 ng/L in the blood sample collected at the time of admission. This value subsequently increased to 110 ng/L at 4 hours and 98 ng/L at 6 hours.

In light of the patient's medication history, specifically the use of cardiotoxic drugs, the presence of a known pacemaker, and elevated troponin levels, a decision was made to proceed with further investigation in accordance with the San Francisco Syncope Guidelines. The patient was subsequently referred to the cardiology department.

The cardiology department's evaluation determined that the patient's DDDR pacemaker had been checked recently, that there was no battery problem, and that it was functioning actively. The cardiologist's echocardiogram revealed a 45% ejection fraction, first-degree mitral insufficiency, aortic insufficiency, and third-degree tricuspid insufficiency. The patient exhibited visible pacemaker leads in the right structures, and the pulmonary artery systolic pressure, as measured by POCUS, was 33+10 mmHg. No wall defect was observed in the patient. During the evaluation period, no instances of acute coronary syndrome were identified. The patient was scheduled for outpatient follow-up, during which it was recommended that they continue their medication regimen of acetylsalicylic acid

100 mg once daily, metoprolol 50 mg once daily, and ramipril 5 mg once daily. It was hypothesized that the patient's syncope could be attributed to the medication they were undergoing.

The patient was monitored in the emergency department, and following the repair of the cut on his nose, his discharge was scheduled. During the discharge examination, the patient was noted to be conscious, cooperative, oriented, and neurologically intact upon his departure from the hospital.

Following discharge, the patient returned to their place of residence but subsequently presented at the hospital 12 hours later. The patient was readmitted to the hospital due to a deterioration in his mental state, characterized by a vacant stare, nausea, and vomiting.

Upon further evaluation, the patient was found to be conscious, cooperative, oriented, and capable of producing natural and meaningful speech. Pupillary reflexes were found to be within normal limits. No indications of lateralization or motor deficit were observed. A thorough muscle examination revealed that the muscle tone in all four extremities was within the normal range. The muscle strength was evaluated and found to be at a level of 5/5.

Vital signs: The patient's blood pressure was recorded at 120/70 mmHg, while their peripheral pulse registered at 76 beats per minute. Additionally, the patient exhibited an oxygen saturation level of 99%, supported by nasal oxygen administration. The patient's electrocardiogram (ECG) revealed a normal sinus rhythm. It was observed that the ECG in question exhibited no significant differences when compared to previous ECGs. No ST elevation was observed.

Despite the absence of neurological abnormalities revealed by the conventional neurological examination, neuroimaging was conducted to rule out the possibility of a cerebrovascular event. A comprehensive evaluation was conducted using advanced

diagnostic imaging techniques, including computed tomography (CT), to ascertain the presence of any bleeding or ischemic lesions within the brain. This meticulous examination revealed no such lesions, indicating that the patient does not have any acute or chronic cerebral vascular abnormalities.

Biochemical analyses revealed an increase in hepatocyte breakdown products compared to the previous day. Alanine transaminase levels were found to be 298 U/L, and acetyl transaminase levels were also found to be 298 U/L. The gamma glutamyl transferase level was measured at 149 U/L. The C-reactive protein level was marginally lower than the previous day, measuring at 65 mg/dL. A subsequent evaluation revealed an increase in the patient's troponin levels when compared to the previous day's measurements. Specifically, the levels were recorded at 121 ng/L at the time of admission and 126 ng/L at the 4-hour follow-up.

In light of the patient's neurological alterations, a consultation was sought from the neurology department. The neurologist's evaluation concluded that the current findings did not indicate an acute cerebrovascular event.

An ultrasound examination was performed to evaluate the patient's increasing hepatocyte damage, revealing a heterogeneous hypoechoic lesion measuring approximately 100 mm in diameter with lobular contours. The evaluation concluded that the metastasis was likely. No abnormalities were observed in the portal and venous systems. The gallbladder exhibited a standard size and thickness of the gallbladder wall. No pathological conditions were observed within the lumen of the bile ducts.

During the consultation with the internal medicine department, it was considered that the increasing hepatocyte damage could be secondary to systemic hypotension caused by the syncope episode. It was

recommended to increase oral intake and follow up at the outpatient clinic.

During subsequent follow-up, the patient exhibited symptoms of hypotension, accompanied by notable signs of cardiac insufficiency that became evident during the patient's observation period in the emergency department. Cardiac arrest ensued and, consequently, the patient expired approximately 18 hours after the initial syncope.

DISCUSSIONS

Cardiovascular system involvement is a significant risk factor for syncope. A cohort study conducted by Framingham revealed that individuals afflicted with cardiovascular disease exhibited a nearly twofold elevated prevalence of syncope in comparison with those not afflicted with the condition.[7]The following text is intended to provide a comprehensive overview of the subject matter.

A review of the literature reveals instances where patients have received carboplatin treatment for 4-6 cycles without experiencing significant adverse effects.[8]The following text is intended to provide a comprehensive overview of the subject matter. Despite its purported benefits, including ease of use and safety after discovery, concerns have been raised regarding its potential cardiotoxic effects,

Figure 1. ECG-1

which are contingent upon mitochondrial function.[9]As demonstrated in previous case reports, carboplatin use has been shown to have cardiotoxic effects.[10]An 80-year-old male patient who was being monitored for testicular cancer and had been treated exclusively with carboplatin (AUC 4) subsequently developed heart failure.[11]The following text is intended to provide a comprehensive overview of the subject matter.

In this case, in addition to the patient's chronic diseases, the borderline OT value and the presence of heart failure indicate that he carries various risk factors. The most significant risk factors for sudden cardiac death include bradyarrhythmias, conditions causing cardiomyopathy, and channel disorders.[12, 13]In addition to the patient's risk factors, the cardiac pump dysfunction that ensued the cardiac syncope attack, primarily due to the burden caused by the medication used, resulted in a progressive condition and ultimately led to the patient's mortality.

In addition to the complex conditions of geriatric patients, the burden placed on cells by oncological treatments can lead to sudden death. In the management of such cases, where numerous predisposing factors are present, caution should be exercised with regard to mortality and morbidity.

Figure 2. ECG-2

Figure 3. Nasal bone 3D image on CT

Figure 4. Facial trauma

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Acta Medica Young Doctors

Original Article

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Accepted Date: 2025-09-02

Yıldız Ö. Artificial Intelligence in
Emergency Response: Which Model Offers
More Reliable Solutions?. Acta Medica
Young Doctors. 02 Eylül 2025;1:30-6.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17038499>

Artificial Intelligence in Emergency Response: Which Model Offers More Reliable Solutions?

ABSTRACT

Objective: This study aimed to compare the readability and interobserver consistency of texts generated by Open AI (GPT) and Google GEMINI in response to emergency medicine cardiovascular questions.

Materials and Methods: Text samples were generated by both models (n=20 per model) in response to a predefined set of questions. The interobserver consistency was analyzed by two independent observers using an Intraclass Correlation Coefficient (ICC). Readability was assessed using multiple quantitative formulas, including Flesch Reading Ease, Fog Scale, and Flesch-Kincaid Grade Level, and the results were statistically compared.

Results: The interobserver correlation for the GEMINI group (ICC = 0.636) was notably higher than for the GPT group (ICC = 0.048), indicating better consistency in GEMINI's output, although neither correlation was statistically significant. Readability analysis revealed that GEMINI texts were significantly more readable than GPT texts across most formulas (e.g., Flesch Reading Ease: GEMINI M=57.00 vs. GPT M=47.00, p<0.001). This suggests GEMINI's output is characterized by simpler sentence structures and more accessible language.

Conclusion: The findings suggest that the GEMINI model outperforms GPT in both interobserver consistency and text readability. These results have important implications for the selection of AI tools in medical education and clinical practice, where the clarity and reliability of information are critical.

Keywords: Gemini, ChatGPT, Readability

Introduction

Artificial intelligence (AI) is being increasingly integrated into emergency medicine education, offering transformative potential in clinical practice and the training of future professionals. AI technologies, particularly large language models (LLMs), are being investigated for their potential to improve diagnostic accuracy, streamline triage processes and optimise resource allocation in emergency situations [1]. These advancements are applicable not only to clinical practice, but also to medical education, where AI can provide novel training opportunities for emergency medicine Professionals [2]. Integrating AI into emergency medicine education involves diagnostic support, workflow optimisation, and ethical considerations [3]. AI systems have demonstrated their ability to improve diagnostic accuracy and support clinical decision-making in emergency medicine. They can process vast amounts of data quickly, providing real-time insights that help reduce diagnostic errors and cognitive biases [4]. Machine learning algorithms are particularly effective in predicting hospital admissions and identifying patients at risk of deterioration, which can be crucial in emergency settings [5]. When compared in an educational context, ChatGPT and Google Gemini reveal their respective strengths and limitations across various domains. ChatGPT is renowned for its conversational depth and capacity to produce comprehensible content, whereas Google Gemini is recognised for its multilingual capabilities and sophisticated natural language processing [6]. Both tools have been evaluated in different educational settings, including language learning, physics education and patient education. In each setting, they have demonstrated unique strengths and weaknesses [7]. Since there are not enough studies in the literature on

the use of CHATGPT and Gemini in the emergency department, we aimed to compare the answers given by CHATGPT and Gemini to emergency medicine cardiovascular questions in this study.

Materials and methods

This study was conducted using an experimental design to compare the performance of the OpenAI (GPT) and Google GEMINI language models in response to emergency medicine cardiovascular questions. A total of 20 text examples were generated from each model in response to a series of predefined emergency medicine inquiries.

A readability analysis was conducted to assess the clarity and accessibility of the text. The readability levels of the texts generated by both models were analyzed using various automatic readability formulas commonly used in scientific articles. The primary formulae employed in this analysis encompass the Flesch Reading Ease, Fogg Scale, Flesch-Kincaid Grade Level, and Coleman–Liau Index.

Statistical analysis

The statistical analyses were conducted using the SPSS (Statistical Package for Social Sciences) for Windows 27.0 program. The data were subsequently classified. Categorical data were defined as percentages and frequencies. The numeric data were defined, and a distribution analysis was performed. Data following a normal distribution were defined as mean \pm standard deviation (SD). For data sets that did not adhere to a normal distribution, the median and interquartile range (IQR) were determined. The chi-square test was employed to ascertain the relationship between categorical data. The analysis of numeric tests that followed a normal distribution was conducted using parametric tests (t-tests). Statistical significance was determined by a p-value below 0.05.

Results

For the GPT group, the mean scores given by Observer 1 and Observer 2 were 4.64 ± 0.64 and 4.72 ± 0.56 , respectively. The intraclass correlation was found to be 0.048, indicating a very low level of agreement between the two observers. The corresponding p-value of 0.524 indicates that this correlation is not statistically significant. For the GEMINI group, Observer 1's average score was 4.52 ± 0.64 , and Observer 2's average score was 4.74 ± 0.82 . The intraclass correlation was calculated to be 0.636, indicating a substantial degree of agreement between the two observers. The correlation was determined to be statistically insignificant, as indicated by a p-value of 0.424. Table 1 presents the comparisons.

This analysis, which compares the readability levels of text generated by GPT and Gemini, reveals some significant differences. According to the majority of prevailing readability formulas, text generated by Gemini has been demonstrated to be statistically more legible than text generated by GPT. Gemini demonstrated superior performance in commonly utilized metrics such as Flesch Reading Ease, Flesch-Kincaid Grade Level, and Coleman-Liau Index. These findings suggest that Gemini employs language that demands minimal cognitive effort and is readily comprehensible to its intended audience. The findings indicate that the Gemini model may be more efficacious, particularly in circumstances where texts must be promptly and readily comprehensible to the intended audience (see Table 2).

Discussion

The integration of AI in emergency care is a rapidly growing field with significant potential to improve patient outcomes and operational efficiency. However, the current state of AI applications, particularly chatbots, in emergency settings reveals several shortcomings and challenges [8]. Evaluations of AI chatbots such as ChatGPT,

Google Bard and Bing AI have shown that they often fall short in terms of accuracy, completeness and source reliability when it comes to providing accurate emergency care advice. These limitations underscore the necessity for further refinement and regulation to ensure their safe and effective use in emergency scenarios [9]. AI chatbots demonstrate intermediate performance in terms of accuracy and completeness, achieving scores of around 50% in these areas. This indicates that, while they can offer some correct information, they frequently omit critical details essential for emergency care [10]. Chatbots perform well in terms of clarity and understandability, achieving a score of 85% in these areas. While the information provided is generally easy to comprehend, it may not always be accurate or complete [11]. A concerning finding is that dangerous information is present in 5–35% of chatbot responses, including incorrect CPR instructions. This poses a significant risk to patients who rely on these tools for emergency guidance [12].

The reliability of the sources used by chatbots is poor; most fail to provide relevant or identified sources for their information [13]. AI has the potential to improve efficiency in emergency nursing by assisting with diagnosis, triage and clinical decision-making. However, challenges such as data privacy, infrastructure reliability, and algorithmic bias must be addressed to realise these benefits fully [14].

Integrating AI into emergency management raises ethical concerns regarding bias, transparency, and public trust. It is essential to develop robust frameworks and guidelines to navigate these challenges and ensure the responsible use of AI [15]. AI can alleviate the physical and cognitive demands placed on EMS personnel, optimise the allocation of resources, and improve the efficiency of responses. Proposed innovations such as exoskeletons and smart glasses are intended to support EMS operations [16]. Successful implementation of AI in emergency medicine requires

adaptation and training of the workforce to overcome technological and ethical barriers. This includes ensuring data privacy and addressing biases in AI decision-making processes [17].

A comparison of ChatGPT and Google Gemini in the context of emergency education reveals the distinct strengths and limitations of each AI tool. Both platforms have been evaluated for their effectiveness in generating patient education materials, focusing on readability, accuracy and addressing specific medical conditions. ChatGPT generally produces more comprehensible content, whereas Google Gemini demonstrates potential in integrating various media and providing succinct responses [18]. These differences highlight the potential of AI tools to enhance patient education in emergency settings, though their application may be influenced by their unique attributes [19].

ChatGPT has been found to produce materials with higher ease scores, indicating better readability and comprehension for patients. This is particularly important in emergency education, where clear communication is essential [20]. Conversely, Google Gemini often generates more concise responses with a higher word count, which can be beneficial in situations where brevity is required [21]. Both ChatGPT and Google Gemini demonstrate high accuracy in generating patient education guides, with inaccuracies being rare. This reliability is essential in emergency situations, where accurate information can significantly impact patient outcomes [22]. ChatGPT's conversational depth enables it to address misconceptions effectively, which is advantageous in emergency situations where patients may have a limited understanding of their conditions [16,17]

It has been identified as a valuable tool for improving communication between patients and clinicians, clarifying discharge instructions and answering care-related questions in emergency settings. However, it also faces challenges, such as the risk of

misinformation and privacy concerns [23]. Google Gemini's multimodal capabilities offer the potential to integrate various media, enhancing the delivery of educational content in emergencies. However, it may struggle with conceptual depth and accuracy in some cases [16-20].

Both AI tools face challenges related to bias, and there is a need for critical evaluation to ensure that they complement, rather than replace, traditional teaching methods. This is particularly important in emergency education, where the needs of diverse patients must be addressed [17,18]. The potential for AI-generated content to perpetuate biases is a concern, highlighting the need for transparency and careful implementation in emergency settings [20-22].

This analysis, which evaluates the correlation between two independent observers, reveals the potential impact of the language model used on consistency between observers. In the GPT group, while the mean scores were comparable, the inter-observer correlation (0.048) remained negligible and did not attain statistical significance. This observation may suggest that observers encountered difficulties in implementing the evaluation criteria with uniformity, or that the evaluation scale lacked the requisite sensitivity to responses that align specifically with the GPT model. Conversely, the inter-observer correlation in the GEMINI group exhibited a significantly higher value of 0.636. This finding suggests that the output generated by the GEMINI model can be interpreted more consistently and similarly by different observers. While this correlation does not attain statistical significance, the substantial discrepancy (a correlation value 13 times higher than that of GPT) signals a noteworthy trend. Future studies should investigate the reasons for this difference (e.g., the output structure of language models, differences in grammar or style) in greater depth. The findings of this study indicate that the selection of language models and the quality of output can directly

impact the consistency of evaluations conducted by human observers.

The findings obtained in this study demonstrate that language models have a significant impact on both output quality and the consistency of these outputs when evaluated by human observers. As indicated by the data presented in Table 1, the inter-observer correlation coefficient for the GEMINI group is notably higher than that of the GPT group. The former group demonstrates an inter-observer correlation coefficient of 0.636, while the latter group exhibits an inter-observer correlation coefficient of 0.048. This finding suggests that the GEMINI model generates output that can be interpreted with greater consistency and similarity by different experts. This consistency is hypothesized to stem from the model's language structure, style, or content, which is characterized by increased clarity and comprehensibility.

The readability analysis, as presented in the second table, lends further support to this interpretation. A comparative analysis of the readability metrics Flesch Reading Ease, FOG Scale, and Flesch-Kincaid Grade Level revealed that GEMINI texts were found to be statistically significantly easier to read than GPT texts. The findings suggest that GEMINI facilitates more straightforward and fluid sentence structures, employs a less intricate vocabulary, and exhibits enhanced overall text flow. These findings suggest that readers utilizing GEMINI's output can comprehend the text more expeditiously and with reduced cognitive effort.

While the correlations presented in the initial table do not attain statistical significance, a discernible pattern emerges concerning the discrepancy in consistency and readability between the two models. The findings, when considered collectively, indicate that GEMINI exhibits superior

performance in comparison to GPT with regard to both readability and inter-observer consistency. This result offers important implications for selecting language models to be used in areas where consistency and comprehensibility are critical, such as scientific articles, educational materials, or public information texts. Future research could provide further insight into this area by investigating the underlying mechanisms of these differences (e.g., algorithmic structures or training data differences) in greater depth.

Limitation

GEMINI has been demonstrated to exhibit superior performance in comparison with GPT with regard to both readability and consistency among observers. These results underscore the pivotal role of language model selection, particularly in contexts where consistency and clarity are paramount, such as in educational materials, scientific texts, and patient information guides. These findings offer future research opportunities to explore the underlying mechanisms behind these differences in greater depth.

Conclusion

The present study evaluated the performance of the GPT and GEMINI language models in the domain of emergency medicine, both in terms of inter-observer consistency and text readability. The analysis indicates that the scores assigned to GEMINI's outputs exhibit greater consistency compared to those allocated to GPT. This finding suggests that GEMINI produces outputs that can be interpreted in a more similar and reliable manner by different experts. This uniformity may be attributed to the model's more lucid and coherent linguistic structure and style.

	Mean±SD	Intraclass Correlation	p-Value
GPT Observer 1	4.64±0.64	0.048	0.524
GPT Observer 2	4.72±0.56		
GEMINI Observer 1	4.52±0.64	0.636	0.424
GEMINI Observer 2	4.74±0.82		

Table 1. Interobserver correlation

	Open AI (n=20)	GEMINI (n=20)	p-Value
Average Reading Level Consensus	10,18±2,24	9,59±1,58	0,171
Automated Readability Index	11,04±0,78	11,38±0,90	0,105
Flesch Reading Ease	47,00±5,64	57,00±4,76	<0,001
Fog Scale	12,20±0,97	11,90±1,01	<0,001
<i>Fesch-Kincaid Grade Level</i>	10,53±0,11	9,80±0,56	
Coleman–Liau Index	13,52±1,11	12,16±1,27	<0,001
SMOG index	9,62±1,33	9,74±0,78	0,366
Linsear Write Formula	77,00±6,41	71,00±5,40	0,001
Forcast readability formula	11,53±0,13	11,26±2,04	0,279

Table 2. Readability comperations

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